

Relationship Between Emotional Intelligence and Examination Malpractice Tendency Among University Undergraduates in Anambra State

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Abstract

The study investigated the relationship between emotional intelligence and examination malpractice tendency among university undergraduates in Anambra State. A correlational design was used in this study. The study was guided by three research questions and one null hypothesis. The population of this study comprises 300 level undergraduates from Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka and 300 level undergraduates from Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University Igbariam. The sample was 851 respondents sample from two universities, Nnamdi Azikiwe University and Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University Igbariam. Data for the study was collected using two instruments titled “Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire” developed by Singh (2004) and “Questionnaire on Examination Malpractice tendency” developed by Arjen (2009). Aggregate scores, Pearson product moment correlation and regression analysis were used for data analysis. The findings indicated that majority of the university undergraduate students have low emotional intelligence. The findings showed that only few of the university undergraduate students have high examination malpractice tendency. The findings also revealed that there is a low negative significant relationship between the emotional intelligence of university undergraduate students in Anambra State and their examination malpractice tendency. It was recommended among others that curriculum experts should develop an effective instructional curriculum that incorporates emotional intelligence skills with the objective of enhancing personal and career success of students.

Key words: Relationship, Emotional intelligence, Examination malpractice, Tendency, Undergraduates.

Introduction

Examinations in Nigerian schools dated back to the advent of formal education in the country in the 1800s and it was patterned after the British system. As such, the 1987 Ordinance

made provision for examinations in schools that have attained the requisite percentage of proficiency (Ajibola, 2018). Examination could also be seen as one of the most objective techniques used in the measurement of learning outcomes at all levels of education in Nigeria and the world over. This is why Ajibola defined examination as the measurement of proficiency in knowledge and skills, either in oral or written forms and evaluating the adequacy of these properties possessed by candidate. Operationally, examination is an assessment intended to measure knowledge, skill, attitude, physical fitness or classification in many other topics such as beliefs.

In Anambra State Nigeria, examinations are either internal or public. Internal examinations are the examinations set by teachers in the form of class tests and end of term examinations. Public examinations on the other hand, are examinations that are conducted in the public interest by recognized examining bodies that were not involved in organizing instruction or preparing students for the examinations. Notwithstanding the importance of examinations in the educational system of the State, the instances of malpractices during examinations have been identified.

Examination malpractice is a global phenomenon occurring in both developed and developing countries. It can be viewed as a wider concept encompassing a set of deliberate but unacceptable behaviors that are against academic rules and regulations of a university or a particular course policy stated in the course outline (Sebek, 2012). In the opinion of Wilayat (2019), it is any illegal act committed by a student singlehandedly or in collaboration with others; like fellow students, parents, teachers, supervisors, invigilators, printers and anybody or group of people before, during or after examination in order to obtain undeserved marks or grades. Oguzie and Nwokolo (2021) viewed examination malpractice as any act or behaviour by any person or group of persons before, during or after an examination targeted to influence positively the outcome of such examination. These malpractices include misrepresentation of identity or impersonation, cheating, theft of other students' work, tampering with the works of others, bringing prepared answers to examination halls, unethical use of academic resources, fabrication of results and showing disregard to academic regulations (Gross, 2013; Owuamanam, 2015). The services have been regarded as academic misbehavior capable of truncating an educational system and as such the tendency is increasing on yearly basis.

In a general term, examination malpractice tendency is a comprehensive term that includes a collection of intentional but unacceptable behaviors that are against the rules and regulations of an academic institution (Amuwa, 2015). According to Oguzie, Oguzie, Nnadi, Mokwelu and Obi (2019), examination malpractice tendency is simply defined as the predisposition to indulge in examination malpractice. Therefore, in the context of this study, examination malpractice tendency

among students can be defined when students portray academic behaviours that do not comply with stated assessment requirements and other institutional policies; when students can behave in ways intended to gain undue benefit in relation to their assessment.

The Nigerian educational institution has witnessed unprecedented upsurge in the rate of examination malpractice tendency particularly in the last three decades (Venatus, 2019; Nwokolo & Oguzie, 2021). For instance, a study conducted in two Nigerian institutions showed that 54.2% of undergraduate pharmacy students had been involved in examination malpractice the preparation of their academic exercises (Ubaka, Gbenga, Sunday & Ndidiamaka, 2013). The sudden surge could be linked to over-population of most higher institutions. Ajibola (2018) explained that one of major reasons for high tendencies in examination malpractice is that most students perceive some courses to be unnecessary, therefore they chose an easy way to pass the course. Ajibola further highlighted three different factors responsible for examination malpractice tendencies; psychological factors, environmental factors and intelligence.

Psychological factors have to do with all the stress that is often induced by parents, peer pressure groups and students because of an examination. In the same vain, psychological trauma of failure or scoring low grades promotes candidates involvement in examination malpractice. Environmental factors refer to the crowded nature of classrooms and examination halls with few invigilators during examination. Obsolete, obscure and inadequate instructional materials can lure candidates to perpetrate examination malpractice. This could be as a result of poor intelligent quotient.

Intelligence quotient (IQ) varies among individuals; often academically weak candidates try to compare themselves with naturally gifted candidates. When the weak students are not able to meet up with the challenges, they resort to seeking external help to pass their examinations. In the view of the fact that examination malpractice tendency continue to occur in universities, demands the determination of some factors that relates to it. Several psychological constructs such as self-efficacy, anxiety level, emotional intelligence, study skills, birth order, personality traits and peer pressure could be factors that constitute examination malpractice tendencies among students (Brown, 2012). This study therefore considers how emotional intelligence correlates with examination malpractice tendency among university undergraduates.

Emotional Intelligence is perceived as a type of aptitude that involves the ability to monitor one's feelings and that of others, to discriminate among them and to use this information to guide one's feeling and thinking (Salovey & Mayer, 2010). According to Nwadinigwe and Azuka-Obieke (2012), emotional intelligence is also defined as the intelligent use of emotions: one intentionally makes one's own emotion work for one by using them to help guide one's behaviour

and thinking in ways that enhance one's result. Emotional intelligence skills enable people to reduce negative stress in their lives, build healthy relationships, communicate effectively, and develop emotional health.

The importance of emotional intelligence is necessary to improving performance and psychological well-being in school work (Cherniss, 2014). If emotional intelligence skills are developed, strengthened and enhanced, students may demonstrate increased levels of personal, academic and career achievement (Vela, 2013). Emotional intelligence as determined by Nelson and Low (2009) has four major skills dimensions of emotional competencies namely-interpersonal skills, leadership skills, self-management skills and intrapersonal skills. Nelson and Low identified the need for more effective development of emotional intelligence skills when they stated that: The qualitative, holistic, emotive and subjective experiences of students are critical to healthy growth and development. Nelson and low further remarked that emotional development of students does not seem important until behaviour becomes problematic and reported. Familiar examples are under-achievement, bullying, attrition, school violence, absenteeism, substance abuse, lack of motivation and psycho educational problems.

It is considered important to note that examination malpractice tendency is a serious problem affecting undergraduate students, their parents, academic and non-academic staff in various institutions in Nigeria, and therefore needs serious attention. The need for further studies, particularly in higher education institutions in Anambra State is motivated by the fact that higher education is the ultimate level of education from where students are likely to directly enter the job market. Students' perceptions of what is institutionally acceptable and unacceptable regarding dishonest practices might therefore contribute to their behaviour at the workplace. In fact, students' inadequate understanding of what constitutes examination malpractice tendency has been shown to correlate with their emotional intelligence (Kusnoor & Falik, 2013).

In furtherance, it could be said that consistent rise in students' numbers and increased diversity in recent past has constituted a major challenge for an increase in examination malpractice tendency facing most higher institutions in Nigeria. This challenge may have been brought about by poor emotional intelligence. It is against this background that this study seeks to investigate the relationship between emotional intelligence and examination malpractice tendency among university undergraduates in Anambra State.

Statement of the Problem

The ideal situation for undergraduate students is proper transition into each level of tertiary education in accordance to the institution's guiding rules and regulations. This would promote examination honesty and as well improve emotional intelligence of students in Universities. But in a bid for students to excel academically, they have engaged in various forms of examination malpractice tendency as highlighted above. These forms of examination malpractice tendency emphasized that undergraduate students' engagement in examination malpractice tendency is high and increasing.

This has been an issue of immense concern to the teachers, counsellors, school administrators and the parents. A good number of efforts have been introduced by government so as to tackle the issue of examination malpractice tendency and factors responsible for its prevalence among undergraduates. However, all these efforts have not really yielded the much needed result, thus creating a gap in knowledge for the study. It is therefore against this backdrop that this study seeks to investigate the relationship between emotional intelligence and examination malpractice tendency among university undergraduates in Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to determine the relationship between emotional intelligence and examination malpractice tendency among university undergraduates in Anambra State. Specifically, the study examined:

1. The emotional intelligence scores of university undergraduates in Anambra State.
2. The examination malpractice tendency scores of university undergraduates in Anambra State.
3. The relationship between emotional intelligence and examination malpractice tendency among undergraduates in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the emotional intelligence scores of university undergraduates in Anambra State?
2. What is the examination malpractice tendency scores of university undergraduates in Anambra State?
3. What is the relationship between emotional intelligence and examination malpractice tendency among undergraduates in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between emotional intelligence and examination malpractice tendency among undergraduates in Anambra State.

Methods

The correlational survey research design was adopted for the study. According to Nworgu (2015), correlational design seeks to establish the magnitude of relationship that exists between two or more variables. The rationale for adopting this design is to determine the relationship between emotional intelligence and examination malpractice tendency among undergraduates in universities in Anambra state. The population of this study comprised 6,868 undergraduates in 300 level in two public universities in Anambra State. This comprises 3,265 undergraduates from Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka and 2679 undergraduates from Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University Igbariam. (Source: Academic Planning Unit, NnamdiAzikiwe University, Awka and Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, 2020/2021 session). The sample size of this study consisted of 298 university students in Anambra State using the multi-stage sampling procedure.

Data for this study was collected using two standardized instruments. The first instrument titled “Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire (EIQ). The EIQ instrument was developed and validated by Singh in 2004. It contains 40 item questions with an internal consistency coefficient of 0.91(Singh, 2004). The second instrument is titled “Questionnaire on Examination Malpractice Tendencies” (QEMT) developed by Arjen (2005). The QEMT contains 13 item- questions with a reliability coefficient of 0.84. Each of the reliability coefficients was considered high enough to judge that the instruments were suitable for this study. The Copies of the questionnaires was administered by the researcher and four research assistants through direct delivery method. Data generated for the study were analyzed using aggregate scores, Pearson product moment correlation and regression analysis.

Results

Table 1: Range of scores on emotional intelligence scores of university undergraduates in Anambra state

Range of scores	N	%	Remarks
40 – 99	602	70.9	Low Emotional intelligence
100 – 160	247	29.1	High Emotional intelligence

Table 1 reveals that 247(29.1%) of the university undergraduate students with the scores ranging from 100 and 160 have high emotional intelligence, while 602(70.9%) others who scored between 40 and 99 have low emotional intelligence.

Table 2: Range of scores on examination malpractice tendency scores of university undergraduates in Anambra state

Range of scores	N	%	Remarks
13 – 32	602	70.9	Low examination malpractice tendency
33 – 52	247	29.1	High examination malpractice tendency

In table 2, it was observed that 247(29.1%) of the university undergraduate students with the scores ranging from 33 and 52 have high examination malpractice tendency, while 602(70.9%) others who scored between 13 and 32 have low examination malpractice tendency.

Table 3: Pearson r on the emotional intelligence of university undergraduates in Anambra state and their examination malpractice tendency

Source of Variation	N	Emotional Intelligence r	Exam malpractice tendency r	Remark
Emotional intelligence	849	1.00	-0.308	Low negative relationship
Exam Malpractice tend.	849	-0.308	1.00	

In table 3, it was observed that there is low negative relationship of -0.308 existing between the emotional intelligence of university undergraduates in Anambra state and their examination malpractice tendency.

Table 4: t-test on the significant of Pearson r of emotional intelligence of university undergraduates in Anambra state and their examination malpractice tendency

N	cal. r	df	cal.t	Pvalue	Remark
849	-0.308	847	7.61	0.000	S

S =Significant

Table 4 indicates that at 0.05 level of significance and 847df, the calculated t7.61 with pvalue 0.00 which is less than the critical 0.05. Therefore the first null hypothesis is not accepted. The type of relationship existing between the emotional intelligence of university undergraduates in Anambra state and their examination malpractice tendency is significant.

Discussion of Findings

The finding revealed that there is low negative significant relationship between the emotional intelligence of university undergraduates in Anambra state and their examination malpractice tendency. This means that emotional intelligence did not influence university undergraduate students' examination malpractice tendency. This finding was in line with the findings of Nwadinigwe and Azuka-Obieke (2012) who found that there is a negative relationship between emotional intelligence and academic dishonesty such that developing emotional

intelligence skills of a student will lead to the enhancement of his/her academic achievement. Following this finding, there is the need to inculcate the development of emotional intelligence skills into the school curriculum. This is considered important because of its impact in improving the academic achievement of students. On the other hand, the finding disagreed with the finding of Okello and Aomo (2018) that there is a weak positive relationship among emotional intelligence, self-confidence and accurate self-assessment and suicidal behavior among the secondary school students. The difference in both findings could be as a result of difference in the opinion of respondents due to geographical location.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that majority of the university undergraduates have low emotional intelligence. It was also concluded that few of the university undergraduates have high examination malpractice tendency. Finally, the study concluded that there is a low negative significant relationship between emotional intelligence and examination malpractice tendency among University undergraduates in Anambra State.

Recommendations

Based on the finding of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Curriculum experts should develop an affective instructional curriculum that incorporates emotional intelligence skills with the objective of enhancing personal and career success of students.
2. Psycho-educational therapy to teach all the dimensions of emotional intelligence should be included in the Nigerian university commission bench mark.
3. Since emotional intelligence significantly predicts academic dishonesty it is recommended that university in Anambra state as well as Nigeria as a whole should explore student's academic achievement and reduces academic dishonesty.

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